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MICROBIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF SOIL FROM KWARA STATE POLYTECHNIC TEACHING AND RESEARCH FARM, ILORIN, KWARA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Soil health is a very significant factor in safeguarding sustainable agricultural practices, particularly in maize production. Thus, the aim of this paper was to assess the microbiological properties of soil from a teaching and research farm in Ilorin East LGA, Kwara State, Nigeria. Auger was used to collect samples from each of the sampling units. A total of 50 composite samples were collected from profile pits of the two-soil series across the 20-hectare using the random sampling technique. Samples collected were dug at 15-30cm from where it was transported to the laboratory in a well-labeled polythene bags. The soil samples were dried, sieved and analyzed in the laboratory to determine their microbiological properties. A combination of methods was used to analyze the samples including the substrate-induced respiration method, sequential technique, spread plate methods and serial-dilution. The data collected were statistically analyzed with the use of descriptive statistic such as mean. The study revealed that the mean values of pseudomonas spp, escherichia spp, nitrosococuuc sp and listeria sp are 17.475, 43.15, 69.5 and 77.5 respectively while mean values of streptococcus spp, protein sp and mucor spp are 2.32, 53.1 and 14.99 respectively. This indicated that the bacteria population and the fungi species are low despite its high organic content. To address these issues, the study recommended the need to appropriate soil management such as application of organic amendments and fertilizers are essential for optimizing crop yields, maintaining soil fertility and. improving the soil health.*

Keywords: Soil Microbiology, Soil health, microbial diversity, Teaching and Research farm,

INTRODUCTION

Soil microorganisms play a vital role in maintaining soil health and fertility. So, soil health is a critical factor in ensuring sustainable agricultural practices, particularly in maize production, which is a staple crop and a key contributor to food security in Nigeria. The importance of soil health encompasses immediate crop yields, influencing long-term agricultural productivity and ecosystem resilience. Healthy soils have the ability to maintain nutrients, support robust microbial communities, and preserve the physical

structure, all of which are significant for the successful cultivation of maize. Biological properties, such as microbial activity and soil organic matter content, play a vital role in soil health. Schloter et al. (2003) discuss the importance of soil microorganisms in nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, and the suppression of soil-borne diseases. A healthy microbial community enhances soil fertility and promotes sustainable crop production. Several studies have emphasized the importance of soil health in sustainable agriculture, highlighting the critical role that soil physical, chemical, and biological

properties play in determining crop productivity and ecosystem stability. Lal, (2015) underscored the pivotal role of soil organic matter in enhancing soil fertility and crop yields, particularly in maize production, noting that maintaining or increasing soil organic carbon is crucial for both agricultural productivity and climate change mitigation. Similarly, Yarima et al. (2025) demonstrated that soil microbiology is involved in nutrient cycling, decomposition of organic matter, and degradation of pollutants.

This view is further supported by Doran and Zeiss (2000), who introduced the concept of soil quality, integrating physical, chemical, and biological factors, and emphasizing the need for a holistic approach to soil management. Karlen et al. (1997) also advocated for an integrated approach, arguing that soil health cannot be measured by a single parameter but by a combination of indicators that reflect the overall condition of the soil. Additionally, Brussaard et al. (2007) explored the relationship between soil biodiversity and ecosystem services, finding that diverse soil microbial communities are crucial for nutrient cycling, pest control, and maintaining soil structure. Their research suggests that practices like crop rotation and reduced tillage can promote soil biodiversity and enhance soil health.

Furthermore, Gregorich et al. (1994) highlighted the impact of agricultural practices on soil organic matter dynamics, demonstrating that methods such as reduced tillage and the use of cover crops can significantly improve soil organic matter levels and, consequently, soil health. These studies collectively underscore the need for a comprehensive approach to soil health assessment, which is essential for developing effective soil management practices that enhance productivity, ensure sustainability, and protect the environment.

Maize is a staple crop in Nigeria and a significant contributor to food security and the economy. However, the sustainability of maize production is closely tied to the health of the soil. Soil degradation, characterized by nutrient depletion, loss of organic matter, and reduced biological activity, can lead to declining yields and increased vulnerability to pests and diseases. Previous studies have shown that comprehensive soil health assessments can provide valuable insights into the condition of the soil and inform management practices that enhance productivity and sustainability. The aim of this study was to assess the biological properties of the soil which include measuring soil organic matter, and microbial activity from a teaching and research farm in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

The study of soil microbiology and its significance in sustainable agricultural productivity is grounded in several key concepts and theories. Paul (2014) and Nannipieri et al. (2003) identified some underlying concepts and theories including microbial ecology, ecological theory, biogeochemical cycling, soil structure and function and symbiotic relationships. The identified theories stressed the understanding of interactions among microorganisms and between microbes and the environment. In addition, microbial ecology focusses on diversity, distribution, and activities of microorganisms in soil. Smith et al (2008) to this extent in their works stressed the significance of mutualisms such as mycorrhizal associations which can benefit plants.

Similarly, there are some theoretical frameworks also relating to the outcome of this work including ecosystem services framework which categorizes benefits such as

provisioning, regulating services (MEA,2005). Furthermore, soil quality concept according to Paul (2014) assessed soil's capacity to function while Smith et al 2003) in their explanation community structure and function which importantly affect the soil health, microbial biomass and activity in addition to microbial functional capacities.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Kwara State Polytechnic Teaching and Research Farm is located at the intercept of latitude 8⁰. 48' North of the equator and longitude 4⁰.52' East of the Greenwich Meridian. It is one of the major teaching and research farms in Kwara State. Covering a 20-hectare area, it has been a significant contributor to the local agricultural economy. According to the School Management, the farm generated approximately 30-million-naira worth of maize during the 2023/2024 agricultural season. This level of productivity highlights the farm's potential. However, to maintain and potentially increase this yield, it is essential to conduct a comprehensive soil health assessment.

The study area as divided into two distinct sections: the upper and the lower sections. Nonetheless, a dichotomy of study area into the upper and lower sections for soil health assessment was centered on nearness to the stream and variation in topography and soil properties. Other contributing factors include soil property variations, hydrological differences, and ecological significance as well as the management implications. Overall, fifty (50) soil samples were collected from profile pits of the two-soil series across the 20-hectare Kwara State Polytechnic Teaching and Research farm to guarantee representative results using the random sampling techniques. Sampling was done at two depths: 0-15 cm

(topsoil) and 15-30 cm (subsoil) in the two sections. Thus, a total of 50 composite samples were collected. The soil samples were dried and sieved and were analyzed in the laboratory to determine their biological properties.

An ecological and microbial study of the Kwara State Polytechnic Teaching and Research farm was carried out using the substrate-induced respiration method, and biodiversity was evaluated through sequencing techniques including serial dilution and spread plate methods. The isolated microorganisms were identified based on their morphological, biochemical, and cultural characteristics. The microbial ecology of the soil series in the Kwara State Polytechnic Teaching and Research farm was assessed. The soil samples were transported. Auger was used to collect samples from each of the sampling unit at 15-30 cm from where it was transported to the laboratory. In well-labelled polythene bags. The data collected from the laboratory analysis were statistically analyzed covering a total of 20 hectares. Descriptive statistic such as mean were used in the analysis of the data.

Standard methods including molecular method, cultural-based methods and direct extraction method were used to determine the microbiological properties of the soil. Molecular method was used to identify and count the quantity of *Pseudomonas* spp, *Escherichia* spp, *Listeria* spp, *Rhizopus* spp and *fusarium* spp while a combination of cultural-based and molecular methods was used for *Nitrosococcus* spp, and *Streptococcus* spp. For Protein sp, direct extraction method using phenol-chloroform was used while microscopic observation and molecular methods were adopted to determine the soil *Mucor*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of soil Microbial parameters of soil from Kwara State Polytechnic Teaching and Research farm, as presented in table 1, revealed critical the microbiological analysis of soil in the Study Area. The results show significant variations between Upper section and Lower Section, which can impact agricultural productivity. The analysis revealed a diverse range of microorganisms in the soil samples. The bacterial isolates included species such as Bacillus subtilis, Staphylococcus aureus, Escherichia coli, Pseudomonas and Klebsiella. Fungal isolates on the other hand included Aspergillus niger, aspergillus flavus, Fusarium spp., Mucor spp. Penicillium spp., and Rhizopus spp. The population density of fungi and bacteria varied across different soil samples, with some areas showing higher microbial loads than others. In addition, this study revealed further that high levels of chemicals from inorganic fertilizers affected soil microbial plants and soil health.

For instance, the bacterial isolates indicate pseudomonas spp (29.6%), escherichia spp (16.9%), bacillus spp (14.8 %) and staphylococcus spp (15.3%) were predominant while streptococcus spp (7.2%) had the least frequency. The fungal isolates revealed the presence of aspergillus spp (41.6 %), rhizopus spp (26.3%) and mucor spp (16.55) were predominant. Fusarium spp (2.1%) had the least frequency under fungal isolates. The organic matter content was relatively low in station a (1.25%) and moderate in station b (3.39%). Organic matter is crucial for enhancing soil structure, water retention, and nutrient availability (Lal, 2004).

The findings of this study align with previous research conducted in similar agroecological zones, which reported low organic matter and nutrient levels in tropical soils (Akinola et al., 2017; Ojo et al., 2018, Oyeyiola et al, 2023). These studies emphasize the need for sustainable soil management practices to enhance agricultural productivity.

Table 1: Microbiological Analysis of the Study Area

Parameters	Upper Section %	Lower section %	Mean
Pseudomonas spp	29.6	5.35	17.475
Escherichia spp	43.3	43	43.15
Nitrosococcus sp	72	67	69.5
Listeria sp	76	79	77.5
Streptococcus spp	1.25	3.39	2.32
Proteins sp	53	53.2	53.1
Rhizopus spp	26.3	21.61	23.955
Mucor spp	16.55	13.43	14.99
Fusarium spp	0.001	0.008	0.0045
Organic matter (%)	1.25	3.39	2.32

Source: Authors' Computation 2025

Table 1 further indicates the bacteria population of the upper section of the polytechnic teaching and research farm soil which was rather low despite its high organic matter content. The soil microbial activities are supported by ph levels of the two soils (4.85-

5.55). The highest number of fungi recorded in the upper section series could be attributed to its having the lowest ph. This according to Alexander (1977) and Fawole et al. (2005) that bacteria thrive in a range of pH 5.5-7.5 while fungi tend to dominate the

acider soils. The lower section of the polytechnic teaching and research farm series had the highest variety of fungi species (see table1) the fungi isolates is made up of five fungi series *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium* (0.00 for the Upper Section and 0.008 for the Lower Section), *Rhizopus*, (26.3 for the Upper Section and 21.61 for the Lower Section) *escherichia* (42% for the Upper Section and 43% for the Lower section) and *streptococcus* (1.25 for the Upper Section and 3.39 for the Lower Section) were possibly able to thrive well in these series due to warm humid condition of the soil Because *Fusaria* are prevalent in the tropics (Marcosus, 1983; Oyeyiola et al., 2023; Yarima et al, 2025).

This study highlights the importance of understanding soil microbiology in sustainable agricultural practices. The distribution and diversity of microorganisms in the soil are influence by physicochemical factors such as pH, organic matter content tend to have a richer microbiota, which plays a crucial role in decomposing organic matter and making nutrients available for plant growth.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated the significance of microbiological analysis in understanding soil health and fertility for sustainable maize production at a teaching and research farm in Ilorin Kwara State, Nigeria. Addressing these issues through appropriate soil management practices, such as the application of organic amendments, fertilizers, and salinity management strategies, is essential for improving soil health and enhancing maize yields in the region.

The study findings in addition, have a number of implications including soil fertility management, sustainable agricultural practices

that promote soil health and microbial diversity which can contribute to more resilient and productive farming systems. The findings can inform efforts to conserve and protect soil ecosystems.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings in this study, the following recommendations were made

- i. Researchers, Research Institutions, farmers and Soil Scientist should ensure regular soil monitoring of soil microbiological properties which can help identify changes in soil health and inform management decisions
- ii. Farmers and agricultural practitioners should adopt sustainable farming practices that promote soil health and microbial diversity such as crop rotation, organic amendments and conservative tillage.
- iii. Concerted efforts should be made to conserve and protect soil ecosystems, including reducing erosion, preserving soil organic matter and promoting biodiversity.
- iv. Capacity building and training programmes should be implemented to educate farmers and agricultural practitioners on the significance of soil microbiology and sustainable agricultural practices.

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